

ADAPTIVE OPTICS METRICS & QC SCHEME

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General

Andersen + : “A comparison of astronomical performance metrics for potential Gemini-North Adaptive Optics systems” (2003)

Davies & Kasper: “Adaptive Optics in Astronomy,” in ARA&A, (2012)

Esposito, S. et al., proc. SPIE, 7736, 773609, (2010)

Cornelissen, S.A. et al., proc. SPIE, 7736, 77362D, (2010)

Marchetti, E. et al., proc. SPIE, 7015, 70150F, (2008)

Kolb, J. et al., proc. SPIE 2012, 2014 (AOF Calibrations)

SPHERE-related work

Fusco et al. 2016, Sauvage et al. 2016 (SPIE) Performance & Low Wind Effect

Milli et al. 2016 (SPIE): Speckle lifetime in XAO coronagraphic images

Other facilities

Bailey et al. 2016 (SPIE) Status and performance of the Gemini Planet Imager adaptive optics system => **necessary for SPHERE!**

Etc.!

Talk by F. Rantakyro

AO EQUIPED INSTRUMENTS

NACO: 2001-2013 (UT4), 2015- (UT1)

SINFONI/MACAO: 2003-

LGSF: NACO (2007-2013), SINFONI (2007-)

VLTI/UTs (MIDI, AMBER, PIONIER) + 4xMACAO: 2004 -

MAD(emonstrator): 2008 (UT3, 1 month)

CRIRES(+): 2002-2014 (UT1) & 2017-

SPHERE: 2014 - (UT3)

GRAVITY/CIAO: 2016 (VLTI/UTs)

MUSE/GALACSI: 2017- (UT4+DSM+4LGSF)

HAWKI/GRAAL: 2017-(UT4+DSM+4LGSF)

ERIS: 2019 (?)

E-ELT (MICADO, HARMONI, METIS, etc.)

etc.

Talk by L. Pasquini

AO? It's now a **ZOO!**

SCAO, GLAO,
MCAO,
XAO, LTAO,
MOAO ...

Performance versus field of view

Performance versus field of view

AO TRADE-OFFS!

AO Performance METRICS?

FWHM: between λ/r_0 & λ/D (diffraction limit, all classical AOs)

Strehl ratio (SCAO, LTAO)

Contrast, speckle lifetime (xAO)

SNR (Spectroscopy)

EE (GLAO...)

Ellipticity
Uniformity (MCAO...)

"M²" Stability
(Interferometry
HC Spectroscopy)

High Strehl (K)
50%

Uncorrected image
FWHM: 0.50"

AO corrected image
FWHM: 0.07"

Left: uncorrected

Right: corrected

"First Light" for NAOS-CONICA at VLT YEPUN
(November 25, 2001)

ESO PR Photo 35a/01 (3 December 2001)

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AO Performance METRICS Scheme?

Strehl ratio? Quick Def.

A Strehl ratio is the ratio of the peak intensity of a measured point spread function (PSF) to the peak intensity of a perfect diffraction-limited PSF for the same optical system,

$$S = \frac{I(\mathbf{x} = 0)}{P(\mathbf{x} = 0)},$$

SPIE 2004

where \mathbf{x} is the position vector, $I(\mathbf{x} = 0)$ is the maximum of the measured point spread function (PSF) and $P(\mathbf{x} = 0)$ is the maximum of the diffraction limited PSF.¹

$$S^* = e^{-\langle \epsilon^2 \rangle}$$

Strehl ratio versus FWHM

NACO “CheckAO” Tests **on** the internal fiber
from 2 days ago (recommissioning)

Which “key performance indicator” is the most pertinent

To assess the internal image quality & global AO calibration?

Bad
Focus!

$Sr = 36 \pm 0.5\%$
FWHM ~ 69 mas

Good
Focus!

Sr = 81.9 +/- 0.4%
FWHM ~61 mas

Strehl ratio versus FWHM

Which "key"
To assess the
Sr is good w

NACO
short/mid term
Health Check

NACO Improvements: Phase Diversity to recover NCPA

OPRA Phase Diversity software
(F. Rigaut, B. Neichel)

4 PSF images with ~known defocus
0, 400, 800, 1200 nm

Reconstructed phase

Diversity Comparison.xlsx

Zernike 5	Zernike	mean
70	7	15
-87	26	10
76	9	15
58	-2	15
72	3	15
0	-170	-50
-122	26	15

OPRA

a(3)	: +33 nm
a(3)	: -61 nm
a(4)	: -75 nm
a(5)	: -3 nm
a(6)	: -4 nm
a(7)	: +16 nm
a(8)	: -8 nm
a(9)	: +4 nm
a(10)	: +6 nm
a(11)	: -3 nm
a(12)	: +3 nm
a(13)	: -5 nm
a(14)	: +13 nm
a(15)	: -24 nm
a(16)	: -18 nm
a(17)	: -31 nm
a(18)	: +9 nm
a(19)	: -4 nm
a(20)	: +16 nm
a(21)	: -13 nm
a(22)	: -24 nm
a(23)	: -18 nm
a(24)	: -31 nm
a(25)	: +9 nm

Elapsed time = 31.232716 sec
458

Zernike offsets (z4-z20)
calculated for the S13/

Slight dependency
with rotator angle

Which “key performance indicators”
 To assess the instrument performance
 Sr is good when it is high

NACO Strehl Ratio

10 year-trend (2003-2013), median and peak performance variations

n?

NACO
 long term
 “history”

PERTINENT METRIC FOR GLAO

EXAMPLE:

**AOF MUSE/WF (1')
+ GALACSI (UT4)**

**AOF HAWKI/Very WF (7.5')
+ GRAAL (UT4)**

Talk by P. Hibon

ASSIST

GRAAL
Hawk-I

Deformable
M2

GALACSI
MUSE

4LGSF

Laser
Room

GALACSI FDR

PERTINENT METRIC FOR GLAO

“seeing enhancer” modes

MUSE/GALACSI GLAO

HAWKI/GRAAL GLAO

SINFONI “no tip/tilt”

Which KPI

is pertinent ?

Internal: Sr OK (Health Check)

On-sky: FWHM (~ok), Encircled Energy

or Energy concentration improvement in a given box

“improve by a factor of 2 the energy concentration in a 0.2 arcsec side spatial resolution element with respect to what is expected in seeing limited conditions”

Sr would be $\ll 1\%$ with/without... (insensitive)

Several KPIs for SPHERE are still being defined or implemented...

For QC0, we decided to rely on a SIMPLE scheme (guide probe IQ/FWHM: **Poor**, **OK**, **Good**, **Very Good**) as we first need to learn and establish correlations

Ideally, the achieved contrast would be a good QC0 metric but it is strategy dependent, requires working pipelines and quick looks and an “alignment” with the ETC / instrument model and response to atmospheric parameters.

LOW WIND EFFECT (LWE)

No Effect

Typical Effect
"Mickey ears"

Strong cases

My Talk
on SPHERE, earlier

DTTS images(every 30s)

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DATA CHAIN & QC0

Science Case/Idea **USER**

Simulate performances

Design OBServations

Set of constraints
versus knowledge/measurement
of the atmospheric conditions

QC grade can depends on
Instrument Health
behaviour versus (many parameters)

ETC/Manual

Choose appropriately

Perform / Classify (QC0)

Deliver Observations

ESO/SciOps

Analyse & Publish
or perish...

Archive

USER

PREDICT, ASSESS, MONITOR

**Astrophysical
Field**

Complex?

~STATIC

**Atmospheric
Turbulence**

Understand

Characterize!

Simulate!

DYNAMIC

**complex
Optical
system**

**including
Telescope
AO**

**Coronagraph
etc.**

**NCPA
AO Cal.
INS Model
HC (QC Param)**

DYNAMIC
& ~STATIC

**Science
Frames**

**Apply Metrics
possible?**

Direct IQ assessment is not easy

Raw or even reduced data can be **NOISY**
for all AO-fed instruments, modes !!!!

PIPELINE / TOOLS are needed

=> data mining, correlations (c.f talk by E. Peña with “sysmon”)

Many times the science frames are **NOT SUITABLE**
to perform uniform AO QC0

=> e.g. no unresolved star (PSF) or undersampling

=> complex mode (coronagraphy, spectroscopy)

=> strategy or science/case dependent!

QC, QCO and QC"-1"

- Identify critical health check QC parameters
- Categorize them: are they used to
 1. measuring Key Performances
 2. monitoring the Instrument Stability
 3. measuring the Quality of Calibration
 4. measuring Atmospheric quantities !
- Keep a history of the changes

Adapted to simple cases

Direct "seeing" limited imaging (FORS2, HAWKI, etc.)

The user's (p2pp) constraints suffice & are well measured/ understood
 The ETC predictions and real performances match!
 (simple FWHM model)

More complex cases are delicate

AO combined with spectroscopy, coronagraphy

- => The user's (p2pp) constraints can be too basic to describe all external conditions that possibly affect the data: tau0, wind, etc.)
- => ETC and real performances do not always match for all modes!
 (e.g complex contrast model)
- => Require experienced operators/astronomers (meanwhile)
 e.g. SPHERE => training!

AO Performance METRICS?

IMPOSSIBLE to use the same metric
for all AO-fed instruments, modes !!!!

DIFFICULT to understand, measure
=> data mining, correlations with
Instrument data, with predictions

Talk by E. Masciadri

NECESSARY to develop a common but versatile
QC / QC0 strategy / **PHILOSOPHY**

=> Analysis Tools

=> Trustworthy ASM 2.0

=> Training!

